

Examination of Glamping Tourism Experiences with Netnography Method: Fethiye Case

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ABSTRACT

The pandemic process and its aftermath have encouraged tourists to explore different types of tourism and pursue new searches, and previously unknown types of tourism have become popular. One of these is glamping tourism, which brings camping and luxury together and offers people hotel-like service. The main purpose of this study is to evaluate tourist experiences by examining the comments made by guests staying at glamping businesses in Fethiye, one of Türkiye's important tourism destinations, on the Google Maps website after their holidays. For this purpose, the netnography approach, one of the qualitative research methods, was used in the study. Netnographic analysis includes examining textual data and researching online communities. In the study, tourist experiences were divided into themes: product-based experiences, relationship-based experiences and activity-based experiences, and then coded according to these themes. In addition, content analysis was conducted by selecting comments relevant to the thematic titles. The research results are important for revealing tourists' experiences regarding the Fethiye destination in the context of glamping tourism, which has become popular in recent years.

1. Introduction

Today, with the development of tourism, various tourism products and services are offered to people with different demands and needs. This innovative approach has a significant impact on tourism. The change in people's perspective on life, their increasing expectations, and their desire to choose tourism types suitable for their own characteristics strengthen this diversity and innovativeness (Aksöz et al., 2020). Visitors want to receive quality service, have different experiences, and spend more time in open spaces and quiet places. Middle and high-income tourists who do not want to forego luxury consumption also want to participate in nature-based activities (Lee et al., 2019).

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In this context, glamping tourism is at a level that will meet the needs of these visitors. Offering more luxurious accommodation and opportunities intertwined with nature compared to traditional camping, glamping tourism aims to increase visitors' satisfaction levels (Brooker & Joppe, 2013).

Glamping is a word of English origin, formed by combining the words glamorous, meaning enchanting and luxurious, and camping, meaning "luxury camping". In other words, glamping is a new tourism product that offers tourists the luxury of modern accommodation and the opportunity to camp freely (Olcay & Turhan, 2017). Glamping, which tends to improve the facilities offered by camping areas and increase the comfort levels of guests, offers tourists the opportunity to have a holiday in the open air (Brochado & Pereira, 2017). Considering the developments after the pandemic and people's desire to have more individual holidays, glamping tourism has become a preferred choice by tourists. In this context, it is extremely important to research new trends and develop strategies in line with the changing tourism market demand (Çelik İlal & Gümüş Dönmez, 2023). Examples of studies on glamping tourism in the literature include (Konak & Özhasar, 2019; Aylan & Çetin Gürkan, 2021; Düzgün, 2021; Adamovich et al., 2021; Güvenol & Sarıbaş Kömürcü, 2022; Pop et al., 2024).

Glamping tourism has become one of the most important tourism trends of the 2020s. The global glamping tourism industry is experiencing a very high growth rate in the Middle East tourism market and in Turkey in terms of international tourist arrivals (Yıldırım & Erkılıç, 2019). In this context, it is thought that glamping tourism should be developed and shaped according to tourist experiences. Tourism products, which have a more abstract structure, can be perceived differently by tourists. For this reason, it is extremely important to know how tourists perceive their experiences in the destination they visit. Based on this, the research question in this study focused on the experiences of tourists staying in glamping establishments in Fethiye. The examination of tourist experience perceptions pertaining to the Fethiye destination and the evaluation of the results within the scope of the research will also contribute to other destinations. The research results are intended to contribute by helping destination managers and marketers adopt a serious and integrated approach to offer a higher quality experience to tourists visiting the destination. It is also intended to provide ideas to entrepreneurs and destination managers who are looking for new ventures in the tourism sector. The research also aims to contribute to the literature by including tourist experiences related to the current topic of glamping tourism.

2. Literature Review

People who are overwhelmed by the crowds and complexity of city life prefer camping and caravan tourism to stay in touch with nature. However, camping and caravan tourism have some difficulties such as cold weather, insects, mud, security and health problems. Those who do not want to face these difficulties, and especially those who want their daily needs to be of a certain quality, have started to seek a different kind of tourism. Glamping tourism meets these demands by offering visitors comfortable and diverse accommodation options in a luxurious way, surrounded by nature. Glamping tourism is a type of tourism in which the service quality, food and beverage services and comfortable hotel accommodation in luxury hotels are designed within the framework of sustainability, and people feel better by participating in recreational activities offered by these businesses (Düzgün, 2021). Glamping tourism has become the newest tourism trend after 2020 and is generally known as luxury camping, which is a combination of the English words "glamour", "luxury", and "camping". As a word,

glamour carries “talismanic qualities. The object has a sparkle and glow about it that enhances the people, objects, and places to which it is attached” (Göktaş & Kızıllırmak, 2017). In academic literature, luxury is often associated with quality, prestige, elegance, exclusivity, value for money, individual significance, and social purpose. In the tourism sector, luxury tourism is based on the foundations of space, time, personalized service, security, health, and privilege (Gross et al., 2023).

According to Grand View Research, the glamping market was valued at \$3.15 billion in 2023 and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 8.7% from 2024 to 2030 (Colesnicova et al., 2024). Visitors who prefer glamping tourism and plan and carry out their holidays accordingly are called “glampers”. Glamping is a tourism product preferred by visitors who adopt a sustainable and healthy lifestyle. Glamping tourists are those who have high incomes, love nature, want to spend their holidays in a luxurious environment, are couples and families, are tourists over the age of fifty, love camping life, want their children to be safe in the camping area, avoid transporting and installing camping equipment, and want to be directly in touch with nature outside of standard hotels and holiday villages (Göktaş & Kızıllırmak, 2017). In addition, those who want to stay away from the intensity and stress of daily life, those who love the wild and want to have close contact with nature, and tourists who love adventure, freedom and independence are likely to seek out travel experiences that satisfy these desires (Çelik et al., 2017). Although glamping tourism is thought to appeal only to the high-income group because the word “luxury” is an open-ended phrase, it can also attract other demographics seeking unique experiences. At first glance, it can also appeal to individuals with different socio-economic characteristics, such as families with children, travelers, couples, and those who want to have an environmentally friendly holiday (Aksöz et al., 2020).

Glamping sites offer their visitors accommodation in a unique, natural environment. They offer accommodation opportunities with various concepts, including not only tents with different designs, but also luxuriously designed tree houses, cabins, and caravans (Boscoboinik & Bourquard, 2012). If we need to classify in more detail, the types of glamping accommodation options can be listed as follows (Ergüven et al., 2015):

- tents (luxury tents, bell tents, safari tents, tipis, domes, etc.);
- cabins (A-frame cabins, cottages, tree houses, igloos, cold-resistant igloos, wooden huts, etc.);
- other (islands, towers, inflatable rooms, floating houses, villas, restored old places, etc.).

Glamping tourism is also seen as environmentally friendly tourism in unspoiled nature. Business owners who provide services with this awareness use natural and environmentally friendly products as much as possible. They mostly offer their own products and additive-free products to their visitors and they attach importance to efficient use of resources and recycling (Önem, 2019). Glamping is a nature-based tourism type and offers its visitors ecological education, nature protection, outdoor activities and natural accommodation. In addition, it provides a creative camping style with high-quality service and innovations, high-quality, innovative outdoor accommodation, prestige, and delicious food. It differs from other tourism activities in that it is environmentally friendly, with minimum consumption of energy resources by environmentally sensitive consumers, use of ecological areas that are compatible with the natural environment, and environmentally friendly materials, organic foods, reuse of materials, and alternative transportation opportunities. For tourists, glamping is important for privacy, security, privilege, accommodation in small groups, and

connection to natural heritage. For managers, it provides the opportunity to develop long-term infrastructure, innovative business models, and revitalize camping. In addition, glamping is based on an ecologically and environmentally sustainable philosophy (Fig. 1) (Pop et al., 2024).

Fig. 1. Glamping as a sustainable form of tourism
Source: Pop et al., 2024, p. 5

Europe is the largest region for the glamping market in 2024. The regions covered in the Glamping Global Market Report (2025) are Asia Pacific, Western Europe, Eastern Europe, North America, South America, the Middle East, and Africa. The countries covered in this report are Australia, Brazil, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Japan, Russia, South Korea, the UK, the US, Canada, Italy, and Spain. There are many glamping destinations around the world. For example, Patagonia in South America is an ideal glamping destination. The destination has many eco-friendly accommodations and the scenery is breathtaking. There are a variety of accommodation options overlooking the lake, surrounded by exotic birds and lush vegetation and rainforest. In Norway, there are capsule-shaped accommodations designed specifically for viewing the northern lights in the Aurora Zone, similar to tents designed for overnight “Aurora Glamping”. There are popular options for glamping throughout the British Isles. There are yurts, Hobbit houses, shepherd's huts, pods, domes, a converted aeroplane in Pembrokeshire, South Wales, and many more options. France is one of the key countries in Europe that promotes glamping, offering a total of 8,000 campsites to choose from, with a range of luxury levels all over the country. Many Eurocamp sites offer experiences between camping and glamping, too. There are permanent basic tents with beds and fridges, as well as large safari tents with their own decks. Domes, yurts, and pods (the standard types of glamping accommodation) are available, especially in rural France (Colesnicova et al., 2024). The Fethiye district of the Muğla province in Turkey is among the glamping tourism destinations. Fethiye has breathtaking views, including its natural beauties, lush vegetation, mountains, and a clean and sparkling sea. Glamping operations in the Fethiye region offer personalized services, carefully selected

activities, and environmentally friendly accommodation opportunities.

The tourism industry is experience-based. Experiences are economic offerings that have different characteristics from goods and services. Successful experiences are situations that the tourist finds sustainable over time, does not forget, wants to repeat, and shares through word-of-mouth marketing. Businesses often want to provide their customers with experiences that are out of the ordinary and unforeseen by their competitors (Cavlak & Cop, 2019). Tourist experience is complex, multidimensional, and highly diversified (Robinson & Getz, 2014). Tourist experience is multidimensional and holistic, involving the complexity of people, organizations, places, actions, objects, and technologies (Osman et al., 2014). Therefore, presenting definitive explanations of tourist experience is fraught with difficulties (Ryan, 2010). Similarly, Larsen (2007) argues that the concept of tourism experience is an ambiguous social scientific construct. Based on this, although existing literature agrees on the importance of tourist experience, there is no consensus among scholars, due to different approaches in defining tourism experience (Akyürek & Kutukız, 2020). Tourist experience can be defined as an individual's subjective evaluation (cognitively, emotionally and behaviorally) of the course of events related to tourist activities before the trip (planning and preparation), during the trip (at the destination) and after the trip (remembering) (Tung & Ritchie, 2011).

Previous studies on tourist experience generally focus on how the tourist experience is formed, the factors affecting the tourist experience, and what the effects of these elements are on tourist behavior (Cavlak & Cop, 2019). Recent studies on tourist experience include the experiences tourism businesses, such as hotels, restaurants, and travel agencies provide to customers (Kim & Moon, 2009; Hosany & Witham, 2010; Walls et al., 2011), show that consumption experience is a combination of emotions and thoughts (Oh et al., 2007; Walls et al., 2011), and examine the effects of emotional elements on the purchasing process (Berry et al., 2002; Ritchie & Hudson, 2009). Tourism destinations are a combination of many tourism-related products and services that offer an integrated experience to their customers. These touristic products and services aim to provide rational and emotional experiences to customers (Cavlak & Cop, 2019). This study focuses on touristic experiences and aims to contribute to the tourism literature by associating them with glamping businesses in the Fethiye region, one of the important tourism destinations of Turkey.

3. Methodology

The main purpose of this study is to determine the tourist experiences regarding glamping. For this purpose, a qualitative research approach was used in the study. Qualitative research provides researchers with a more comprehensive understanding of the participants' feelings, thoughts and ideas (Baxter & Jack, 2008). Therefore, qualitative research provides rich empirical outputs for researchers to derive relevant theoretical insights (Creswell et al., 2007).

Within the scope of this research, tourist experiences regarding glamping tourism on the Google Maps website were evaluated using the netnography method, which is one of the qualitative research methods. The netnography method, which is carried out by analyzing data in the virtual environment, has some advantages over its classical counterpart, ethnography. People can express their ideas much more clearly in virtual environments than in real life (Cebeci & Küçükkancabaş Esen, 2018). Apart from this situation, it is possible to reach people who are very difficult to reach face-to-face/to meet in person within the scope of a subject through open sources in the virtual

environment very quickly (Sandlin, 2007).

Firstly, in the study, comments on the Google Maps website belonging to businesses serving in the Fethiye destination were determined. When the literature was examined, it was observed that comments on the Google Maps website were used as a reliable data source in various studies (Ateş & Sunar, 2019; Halaç et al., 2020; Koç & Şahin, 2023; Dinç & Argan, 2024). This research selects comments from the Google Maps website, because this platform contains the most valuable comments. To this end, a search was made with the words “Fethiye glamping” on the Google Maps website. Within the scope of the research, 309 customer comments on the Google Maps website until April 25th, 2025, were identified. The glamping businesses identified on the site were taken one by one, and the comments were recorded in a file. The researchers examined the recorded comments and carried out the theming and coding process. The themes were determined by the work of Akyürek and Kutukız (2020). In their study, Akyürek and Kutukız (2020) examined tourist experiences as product-based experiences, relationship-based experiences, and activity-based experiences. Within the scope of this research, the researchers read the comments individually and coded them according to these three main themes. In addition, the researchers read the comments one by one and categorized them as positive and negative. Then, content analysis was conducted by selecting comments relevant to the theme headings. The content analysis expanded the scope of the research by providing examples from comments appropriate to the theme.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. General findings

Research findings show that visitor comments made on Google Maps about glamping businesses in the Fethiye region were examined. A search was made on the Google Maps website with the keyword “Fethiye Glamping”, and 5 businesses were identified. 112 comments were recorded regarding business 1, 85 comments regarding business 2, 13 comments regarding business 3, 176 comments regarding business 4, and 23 comments regarding business 5. Comments regarding glamping businesses until 25 April 2025 were examined. The closest comment to this date was 2 months ago, and the farthest comment was 7 years ago. It was determined that comments were made in different languages. The number of comments English 122, Russian 34, German 17, Ukrainian 6, French 4, Italian 3, Dutch 1, Arabic 1, Catalan 1, and Korean 1. The remaining comments were in Turkish.

4.2. Themes and sub-themes regarding tourist experience components

Tourist experiences are categorized into three main themes, which are further divided into sub-themes with content analysis. The main themes consist of product-based experiences, relationship-based experiences and activity-based experiences. Sub-themes related to product-based experiences are given in Fig. 2.

When Fig. 2 is examined, 10 sub-themes belonging to the theme of product-based experiences were identified. These sub-codes consist of price/value, quality, awareness, cleanliness/hygiene, story, naturalness, diversity, originality, being first/different, and service/presentation.

Under the product-based experience theme, comments were examined under the codes: price/value, quality, awareness, cleanliness/hygiene, story, nature, variety, originality, first, and service. A total of 215 positive and negative comments were made under this theme. The price/value code was defined as: “price”, “cheap”, “expensive”.

There are 23 positive and 9 negative comments regarding price. Three positive comments were made regarding the cheap, four positive and one negative comments were made regarding the expensive, and a total of 49 comments were counted under this code.

Fig. 2. Sub-themes related to product-based experiences

Table 1. Product-based experiences

	Positive	Negative	Total
Price/Value	30	19	49
Quality	3	3	6
Awareness	3	0	3
Cleanliness/Hygiene	37	9	46
Story	2	0	2
Naturalness	74	8	82
Diversity	5	0	5
Originality	4	0	4
Being first/Different	11	2	13
Service/Presentation	7	0	7
Total	174	41	215

Under the product-based experience theme, comments were examined under the codes: price/value, quality, awareness, cleanliness/hygiene, story, nature, variety, originality, first, and service. A total of 215 positive and negative comments were made under this theme. The price/value code was defined as: “price”, “cheap”, “expensive”. There are 23 positive and 9 negative comments regarding price. Three positive comments were made regarding the cheap, four positive and one negative comments were made regarding the expensive, and a total of 49 comments were counted under this code.

A total of 6 comments were received regarding the quality code, 3 positive and 3 negative. 3 positive comments were made regarding the awareness/recognition code. A total of 46 comments were made under the cleanliness/hygiene code, 37 positive comments and 9 negative comments. 2 positive comments were made under the story code. A total of 82 comments were determined under the nature code, of which 74 were

positive and 8 were negative. A total of 5 positive comments were made regarding the diversity code. A total of 4 positive comments were made under the originality code. A total of 13 comments were made under the first/different code. Of these, 11 were positive and 2 were negative. 7 positive comments were made under the service/presentation code. Some of the statements of tourists regarding this theme are given below:

“A wonderful place and environment surrounded by nature. We were very pleased with the food, cleanliness and environment. There were many beaches, natural beauties and historical places nearby to visit. We were able to have a fully enjoyable, comfortable and affordable holiday without getting bored. It is also a suitable business for pet owners.”

“It is a very beautiful place, the hosts are very kind and attentive, the rooms are in good condition. The atmosphere provides a friendly feeling, making it very good for couples or small groups or even retreats. There is a place to do yoga. The food at the restaurant is also very delicious and affordable.”

“A truly unique place! It is the best beach camp ever, very spacious, with a beautiful beach, that is not too crowded, and the sunsets are amazing. There is a bar and restaurant, the food was delicious and the staff were very welcoming and friendly. The hike to the waterfall was very invigorating. A very relaxing place with many options to spend quality time in nature and boat trips to explore the area. I can only recommend it.”

“This place is truly magical!! Everything is perfect here—a magnificent location, clean air, delicious food. After a busy day of hiking, you experience indescribable emotions when you sit in front of a warm stove with crackling wood and eat a delicious dinner prepared by the owner of this wonderful place!”

“A unique, mystical environment, surrounded by nature, a calm and peaceful holiday... We were satisfied...”

“I had the glamping experience for the first time in my life and I liked it. The rooms were nice, there was hot water, a nice breakfast and the host was really kind. I recommend it.”

“A wonderful holiday experience offered with magnificent nature, scenery, pine mountain air, natural and warm hosts. Opening up to infinity from every corner, the views you have never seen before, offer a unique visual beauty at every hour of the day.”

“It is worth a try for people who are tired of the traditional hotel experience and are looking for a different holiday. It is a holiday where you can stay in a tent, watch the stars and not compromise on your comfort.”

Fig. 3 shows the subthemes of the relationship-based experiences theme.

Fig. 3. Sub-themes related to relationship-based experiences

When Fig. 3 is examined, it is seen that relationship-based experiences are grouped under four sub-themes. These codes are: relations with local people, relations with employees, relations with local managers, relations with other tourists.

Table 2. Relationship-based experiences

	Positive	Negative	Total
Relations with local people	0	0	0
Relations with employees	46	4	50
Relations with local managers	0	1	0
Relations with other tourists	0	0	0
Total	46	5	51

A total of 51 comments were categorized under the relationship-based experiences code. No conclusions were drawn regarding the theme of relations with local people or other tourists. A total of 50 comments were identified under the code of relations with business employees/staff, of which 46 were positive and 4 were negative. Only one negative comment was identified regarding local administrators. Some of the comments made by tourists about relationship-based experiences are as follows:

“I had a wonderful two nights here. The host is wonderful and speaks perfect English. The property is beautifully decorated in the style of two English and two Turkish palaces. A different and cheap place.”

“Calmness, wonderful nature, cleanliness and plenty of oxygen. Food is valuable. On the Lycian way. Foreign tourists know more than we do about certain attractions, which is why they come to visit.”

“It was an incredible experience, with a lovely host who is very knowledgeable about local attractions and contacts to arrange your transfers. There is pure peace and tranquility here. It is a pleasure to be with Corinne. I wish I could visit more often because the visits are never long enough.”

“A wonderful establishment... You feel more at home than in a business setting. I had the opportunity to stay for two days during the Lycian Way walk, the owners are very friendly and sincere people, and so are the employees.”

“A magnificent place, quiet and peaceful. The employees are very friendly, it is impossible not to admire the owner.”

Fig. 4 shows the sub-themes of activity-based experiences.

Fig. 4. Sub-themes related to activity-based experiences

The number of sub-themes created for the activity-based experiences theme by tourists participating in glamping tourism in the destination of Fethiye is 4, and these themes consist of educational/instructional activities, entertaining activities, relaxing/peaceful activities, and healthy activities.

Table 3. Activity-based experiences

	Positive	Negative	Total
Educational/Instructional activities	1	0	1
Entertaining activities	7	0	7
Relaxing/Peaceful activities	84	6	90
Healthy activities	4	0	4
Total	96	6	102

A total of 102 comments were identified under the theme of activity-based experiences. One positive comment was made regarding educational/instructional activities. Seven positive comments were identified regarding educational activities. A total of 90 comments were identified regarding relaxing/peaceful activities, with 84 positive and 6 negative. Four positive comments were identified regarding health activities. Examples of comments made regarding activity-based experiences are given below:

“Delicious and healthy food makes you feel at home. I enjoyed the delicious vegan/vegetarian food at the roadside kitchen.”

“You find yourself in a very sincere and warm nature, in this establishment that has no trace of the stifling atmosphere of the city, you are welcomed by its warm-hearted and energetic owner. A place where you can find the peace you are looking for, where you can rest and spend time under the endless sky at night, or rather a place where you can feel at home. You can easily maintain your energy throughout the day with healthy and satisfying food.”

“The hotel offers a peaceful stay in touch with nature. The rooms are clean and comfortable, and the staff is extremely friendly and attentive. It is an ideal place for a short getaway. I definitely recommend it.”

“This place, away from the noise of the city, embraced by nature, where bird sounds are never missing, has a good attitude towards plastic, is friendly to guests, where you can rest, and is within walking and cycling distance of many points (Soğuksu, Kelebekler Vadisi, Ölüdeniz, Kayaköy). A facility that those who are tired of holiday villages and 5-star concepts and want to immerse themselves in oxygen and peace should definitely visit.”

“If you are looking for a friendly, free, comfortable and fun place in nature, away from city life, then Butterfly Valley. It offers a comfortable tent experience, friendly staff, magnificent sea views, and natural surroundings.”

5. Conclusion

Changing tourism trends are causing new and different types of accommodation to emerge. The increasing tendency to return to nature, along with growing ecological and sustainability awareness among tourists, is causing an increase in demand for nature-based camps and similar accommodation businesses in the tourism sector. In addition, this trend is contributing to the expansion of such businesses. Glamping tourism, which combines camping and luxury, is one of the tourism trends that has been

in demand in recent years. The experiences of tourists staying in Glamping businesses in the Fethiye region were discussed in the research.

In the research, visitor comments were examined under the themes of product-based experiences, relationship-based experiences and activity-based experiences, which are components of tourist experience. Product-based experience regarding glamping tourism was the theme with the highest number of comments (215). It was determined that the guests staying in glamping facilities in the Fethiye region made positive comments about nature/naturalness, cleanliness/hygiene and price. Although these findings coincide with the characteristics of glamping tourism, very few comments about quality were found. Businesses should pay more attention to this issue.

Although glamping is considered to appeal only to high-income groups at first glance, since the word “luxury” is an open-ended phrase, it appeals to individuals with different socio-economic characteristics, such as families with children, couples, and travelers (Aksöz et al., 2020). According to the research findings, the comments examined include the following: “The dormitories are absolutely magnificent and very luxurious”. “Everything has been considered to make you feel very comfortable, designed like a luxury hotel room, a wonderful environment where you can start the day with a unique view and enjoy nature and the sea together”. “The luxury tents are stylishly furnished and offer a perfect blend of comfort and adventure”. “The views were unique and the domes were very luxurious”. It has been determined that these comments are in line with the “luxury” theme of businesses' glamping offerings. In the research conducted by Olcay and Turhan (2017), it was determined that the fee for the glamping service provided in Turkey is cheaper than the fee for the glamping service provided in foreign tourists' own countries. At the same time, tourists who are bored with sea-sand-sun tourism in Turkey have started to prefer a calmer and relaxing tourism product. The results of this study are similar to those of the study conducted by Olcay and Turhan (2017).

The study, conducted using the netnography method, using the case of Fethiye, deeply examined the reflections of glamping tourism experiences in online environments. The findings show that glamping guests in Fethiye are significantly affected by elements such as being in touch with nature, luxury and comfort, unique view, variety of activities and personalized service in their accommodation experiences. Guests emphasize the positive aspects of these experiences, especially in the visual and textual content they share on social media, and express how glamping differs from traditional camping and hotel accommodation.

5.1. Recommendations

The following recommendations are made in line with the findings obtained from the study:

- Glamping facilities in Fethiye can highlight the natural and cultural richness of the region. Using local materials in facility designs, offering local flavors, and adopting environmentally friendly practices will authenticate the guest experience and contribute to sustainable tourism.
- Properties can encourage guests' social media sharing, engage with them, and use these platforms as an effective marketing tool. Visually focused content and experience stories in particular will play an important role in attracting potential guests.

- Activity options can be diversified to appeal to guests' different interests. Region-specific experiences (e.g., boat tours, Lycian Way walks, local workshops) can be integrated into glamping accommodation.

- Studies can be conducted to understand the expectations and preferences of the guests in advance, and personalized services can be provided during the stay. This will increase guest satisfaction and the likelihood of guests returning.

- Regularly examining the online reflections of glamping tourism experiences using netnographic methods will be beneficial in understanding changing guest expectations and gaining a competitive advantage.

When conducting a study on glamping tourism experiences in Fethiye using the netnography method, it is essential to acknowledge the inherent limitations that may affect the outcomes and the interpretations of the research. Here are several key limitations to consider:

- The research focuses solely on online data, specifically from social media platforms, forums, and blogs where glamping experiences are discussed. This digital footprint may not capture the full spectrum of tourist experiences, as it excludes insights from those who do not engage in online discussions or whose experiences are shared in other formats, such as personal diaries or offline interviews.

- The anonymity and varying authenticity of online contributors present a challenge. Participants may embellish, understate, or misrepresent their experiences due to the lack of accountability in digital spaces. This can lead to skewed perceptions of glamping experiences that may not accurately reflect reality.

- Fethiye, as a diverse tourist destination, attracts visitors from various cultural and linguistic backgrounds. The research may be limited by language barriers, as not all online content is available in English. Additionally, cultural nuances in communication can affect the interpretation of data, potentially leading to misunderstandings or misrepresentations.

The findings from the Fethiye case may not be generalizable to other locations or types of tourism experiences. Fethiye's unique geographical, cultural, and social characteristics may mean that glamping experiences there differ significantly from those in other regions, limiting the broader applicability of the study's conclusions. By acknowledging these limitations, researchers can better understand the constraints of their study and take steps to mitigate their impact, ensuring a more robust and credible examination of glamping tourism experiences in Fethiye.

These results and recommendations provide a framework to further increase the potential of glamping tourism in Fethiye and maximize guest satisfaction.

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